

Exploring the Impact of Family on the Wellbeing in *The Lost Daughter*

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Abstract:

*African American writer and activist from USA Mary Luana Williams (1967-) has published her autobiography entitled *The Lost Daughter* in 2013. Mary is the fifth daughter of Black Panther activist Randy Williams and Mary Williams; she is named after her mother. Born in 1967, a period of the Civil Rights Movement, Vietnam War of 1965, and Black Panther Activities, Mary experienced a period of transformation and transition in her childhood. The African American family background of socio-political inequality, father's activism through Black Panther Party and imprisonment, mother's work for Black Panther Party, work as the first welder woman, and struggle for survival with six children and exploitation as African American made Mary's life tragic and led it to physical and psychological trauma and predicament. In this darkness Jane Fonda, Hollywood actress and social activist, arrived in her life as a ray of hope. Jane's camp at Santa Barbara Laurel Springs summer camp for children paved a new path of development for Mary. In the course of time Jane adopted Mary. Mary's journey from her devastating biological family to reformative adopted family completely transformed her life. Mary visits her biological family in Oakland, California after thirty years and then contemplates on the journey of her life from Oakland to Los Angeles where change in the familial background has a great impact on her being a social activist and a successful African American writer. The present article focuses on the impact of family on the development of an individual with reference to Mary's life as reflected in her autobiography *The Lost Daughter*.*

Keywords: *Family wellbeing, Dysfunctional family, Individual Development, Impact of Familial Background, The Lost Daughter, Mary Williams*

According to Indonesian writer and research scholar Soefandi and Pramudya (2009), 'the family is a social group consisting of two or more people who have blood ties, marriage, or adoption. Families can also be interpreted as small social groups consisting mostly of fathers, mothers, and children, which has a profound effect on children's socialization process. The family is a household environment where there are some people who still have blood or marital relationships.

As per the above definition Mary's family is her adopted family of Jane Fonda and she also

get reunite with her biological family. Mary Williams in *The Lost Daughter* (2013) presents her journey from disintegrated and dysfunctional biological family to balanced and organized adopted family.

Healthy family dynamics have healing power that functions like beckoning light for a person. Family with a healthy emotional bond, characterized by mutual support, intimacy, and warmth without compromising anyone's autonomy is called as functional family. It supports emotional well-being, less stress, and overall health. Functional family is a support

system for personal growth and it helps to rebuild sense of self-worth in a person. Dysfunctional families are generally characterized by unhealthy behaviour and improper roles played by family members. It can deeply impact emotional well-being, social awareness and support that an individual seeks from family. Dysfunctional families can have a profound impact on mental health and influence relationships, communication, and the way to cope with challenges in life. In dysfunctional family communication is poor, emotions are ignored or suppressed, and boundaries are often blurred or rigid. It may affect the well-being of its members. When members of a family unit endure a traumatic event like abuse, neglect, loss, or other harmful circumstances, it can result in family trauma, marked by emotional or physical distress. Dysfunctional family lacks of emotional support or has emotional abuse. Growing up in a dysfunctional family can lead to emotional struggles such as anxiety, depression, frustration, low self-esteem. Adult children of dysfunctional families may carry unresolved issues into adulthood, affecting their emotional well-being and ability to maintain healthy relationships. Over time, unresolved issues can contribute to Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) from which Mary also suffered. Jane cultivates healthier relationships to come out from anxiety, depression, family trauma and appoint a therapist-individual counseling for Mary. She successfully comes out of the mental stress and trauma and enjoys world around. Mary and her sister Teresa develop self-care therapy that build a supportive network to get rid of their family, it fosters resilience and both develop their lives.

Mary presents her life related to two families, the first her biological disintegrated and dysfunctional African American family and the second one her adopted well balanced family of Jane Fonda and her children. The change in the

family at the age of fourteen has affected Mary's life greatly and brought transformation in her life. Mary's parents were activist in Black Panther Party. Her father was arrested and imprisoned for seven years and mother failed to shoulder the responsibility of the family. Her mother's addiction of alcohol, father in the prison, sister's acceptance of the prostitution, sexual abuse and gender-based violence, domestic violence, poverty and unequal treatment as African American all made her life in Oakland tragic and pathetic. In addition to this, sexual assault at the age of thirteen and lower grades in education lead Mary to anxiety and frustration. She has a ray of hope and better future with Jane Fonda when Jane convinced her that 'if she improves her grades, she will allow Mary to live with her.' It motivated Mary and she took efforts to improve her grades and at last left her troublesome family and joined Jane's family in Los Angeles.

At the outset Mary writes about her journey back to her family after thirty years. She says, "I once heard ...families are like fudge, mostly sweet with few nuts. But family can also be like a country. It can thrive in times of prosperity...embroiled, in a senseless conflict...I know I once had a family like this. She has tried to weave moments of peace, despair, and resurrection. (1 Williams)

As research has shown, 'The childhood experiences during this period can have a positive or negative impact on the development of the brain. Children who are raised in nurturing environments of love, care and support can develop healthy attachments, relationships of trust, security and a good self-esteem. Infants who grow up in unconducive environments characterized by abuse and neglect tend to feel unloved, unappreciated and unwanted. Such children may avoid building intimate and social relationships later in life as they find it difficult to trust other people. They develop fear of their

environment and view the world as a dangerous place' [2].

Mary also has impact of her childhood experiences. Born in the circumstances of turmoil, She experienced rebellion, revolution, and police brutality in her childhood. Her father, Louis Randolph Williams was captain in the Black Panther Party and was imprisoned for seven years. Mother used to take all children to meet father once in a week. But afterwards these visits became rare and eventually stopped. Mary felt sorry for it but her sister Deborah informed her about the dispute between parents and said, 'it is better that he is away from the family.' Deborah says, 'they fought so badly one night. Daddy ripped Mama's clothes off and beat her badly...It is better he stays where he is' (Williams 7). Mary's parents got separated by divorce, still father Randy used to meet the family. Mary feels proud of her father as he is revolutionary and fought for the community. Her father's brother, Uncle Landon emerged as father figure for them and enrolled them for the Summer Camp organized by Jane Fonda. They enjoyed weekends with movies, group dance and playing together. Thus, the large family cope with the stress of living in a small apartment. (13 Williams).

Poverty and single parent are one of the major issues in the family. Due to poverty, they can't get basic necessities like clothes and food properly. Mother needs to manage it on a meager income source. Mother gets frustrated with six children. Once she reports to her friend, 'I can't have nothing! They keep tearing everything up.' (Williams p. 15). Living in Ghetto-like conditions, deprived childhood, poverty and lack of resources affected family relationships and support. Mary noticed, 'My mother's relationship with the rest of us was cordial, friendly at times but...not affectionate...There was a sense of duty...to keep us clothed and fed but never kisses

and hugs...and I love you.' (Williams 28) In this way, Family responsibility was a burden. On the contrary, Jane Fonda always cares even for small things and shows her love verbally as well as physically with touch, kiss or a hug. It supports Mary and motivates her.

After divorce, father used to meet children but it was formality to provide groceries and clothes. Mary notices these visits as disciplinary encounters. In the Fonda family also, there is divorce but after divorce Tom Hayden maintained healthy emotional bond with all children including Mary, even though Mary is an adopted child.

Quarrel between parents and siblings, verbal confrontations are regular happenings in dysfunctional families. Deborah became a prostitute and beaten severely by her father. She left the house and decided to live alone. Deborah, as an elder sister, used to keep the house together 'in her absence the sturdy home was.... a lean to in a storm. There was nothing who could hold them together. (Williams 42). The family gets scattered. Mary's other sister Donna was pregnant at the age of fifteen. Out of ignorance she used to ask her siblings to walk on her stomach to hide her pregnancy. But it resulted in premature delivery. The stress in the family increased. Donna found a boyfriend and left the house and went to Texas with her baby. Mother's frustration and addiction to alcohol ruined the family. Sister Teresa got scholarship, developed her career as a college professor. Uncle Landon enrolled the remaining three children - Mary, Louise, Andy to Laurel Springs summer camp by Fonda. Teresa went to hostel on the basis of scholarship, Louise also left home, and Mary was alone at home. Mary feels alone at home. As Mary was interested in acting, she went for audition and there a man called David raped and exploited her. 'The worst part was feeling that I could not talk to anyone about my problems. Personal problems were not

shared in my family, especially if they are related to sex. (66 Williams). So, Mary did not talk about the rape or sexual exploitation to her mother. As suggested by Jane Mary talked about the rape to her uncle and then to her mother. About her father she responded to her uncle, 'I didn't have any faith, my father coming to my defense.' (86 Williams)

In the Spring Laurel camp, Mary talked about the rape to the counselor and then Jane came to know about it. Jane discussed with Mary about the assault and asked her to think about her future. Mary replied, 'I hardly ever thought about my future. I assumed to lead a life similar to my mother's, sister's or other women in the community. (84 Williams) Then, Jane Fonda assured her that she will help Mary to get out of Oakland if she improves in her school grades. Jane will take her to her family at Santa Monica. With Jane's proposal enthusiasm come in Mary Williams's life. Mary feels, 'she (Jane) threw me a lifeline and I grabbed it.' (84 Williams). Then, Jane adopted Mary. When Mary left her family and Oakland she feels as if 'unburdened myself from a painful secret.... and was up to an adventure... towards Los Angeles into the care of Jane Fonda. (85 Williams).

Fonda family was opposite to Mary's earlier family. On airport she was welcomed by Jane and Troy, now brother to Mary. They embraced her. The public display of affection was a bit overwhelming. This family was touchy-feely. Back rubs, hugs, kisses on mouth were normal. (Williams 90). Jane Fonda was Hollywood star, social worker, activist and celebrity. It was completely different life for Mary - safe, secure, comfortable and luxurious. Jane prepared food even bed for her. Sister Vanessa shared her room with Mary. It was life of abundance. Here, parents never took their frustration out on the children. Everyone has schedule and remains busy and still finds time for

each other. Mary was adopted by Jane and it proved a blessing for her. Mary mentioned one incident between Father Tom Hayden and son Troy at the business meeting. At the time of dinner Troy began to doze off, then Tom cradled him gently and rocked him. Mary found this scene tender and intimate. She never saw father so openly affectionate with the child. Even the care and love of Jane which she never experienced earlier makes Mary emotional.

Due to earlier pathetic experiences, Mary suffered from Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD). A counselor-therapist was appointed for her. Mary had fear of the crowd, nightmares, and panic attacks. Jane asked her to focus on the future and education. Mary obtained diploma and presented it to Jane as she writes, 'it was because of her I have it' (105, Williams). Jane also supported needy and worthy students from the society.

Mary was surprised with divorce of Jane and Tom as she never saw them to quarrel openly. She writes as per her earlier experience, I grew up in a house where one expressed unhappiness openly, vehemently and often violently. (116, Williams) The divorce was painful but did not affect the children. On the Thanksgiving Day, all gather together and express gratitude.

Like Jane, her husband Ted Turner was also a social worker and activist. Their work makes Mary to dedicate her life to social work. Parent's activities motivate and guide children. Mary feels proud of Jane's work for environment conservation, nonprofit organization's work for Georgia Campaign for adolescent pregnancy prevention, Ted's work for environment protection. This creates a desire in Mary to work for others.

Mary gets the news of the death of her sister Deborah. She held her mother responsible for the tragic death of Deborah. She blamed mother and said that 'My departure from her

negligent care had spared me a similar fate. (151, Williams) Through Facebook Mary Williams gets connected with past biological family and meets her sisters, uncle, cousin and mother. But she resolves to live with Jane as she tells her, 'I am going to be where I belong. With you.' (300 Williams)

At the end Mary quotes, Joseph Brodsky Nobel Prize winning Russian American poet and essayist, 'No matter under what circumstances you leave it, home does not cease to be home. No matter how you lived there-well or poorly.' (300 Williams)

This quote highlights enduring support of home even though members are away from it, home and family are the lifelong support for a person., At the outset Mary quotes Rita Dove, 'All of us have moments in our childhood where we come alive for the first time. And we go back to those moments and think. This is when I became myself.'

Childhood moments of creativity, freedom, love and innocence help to boost us throughout our life. In dysfunctional families, communication is replaced with shouting, screaming, arguing and silence. Healthy functioning families, on the other hand, exhibit harmony, love, care and support for each other; the home is the safest environment where they are able to express themselves, and members have a sense of emotional, mental and physical wellness. In healthy functioning families, conflict, disagreements and differences are resolved in a healthy manner that is beneficial to all concerned.

Family has great influence on the children's development. The family system represents the most proximal social environment for children. Frequent or high-level conflict within the family including arguing, competition and criticism between family members is associated with childhood depression and anxiety. A healthy and positive atmosphere within

the family provides a conducive environment for mental health in children. It mostly includes open communication, strong interpersonal relationship between children and parents, harmony and cohesion between family members, space for children to develop healthy habits. Family plays a significant role in the development of an individual everywhere in the world. Human beings are born in the family but grow up with parental concern and under parent's care, and obviously in the company of siblings and other family members. In the process of socialization of an individual, family is the first educator, and also structures religious and moral background for a child. Physical and psychological development that is physical refers to biological growth-that includes body functions- walking or talking and psychological development that covers spiritual, emotional and moral development in a systematic and progressive way and a balanced family.

Mary Williams experiences both kind of lives, a life of deprivation at Oakland and abundance and comfort at California with Jean Fonda. She visits Africa, lives there and teaches English in Morocco, and Studies health issues and problems of African people. She also works for CDC- Centers for Disease in Atlanta and travels to Tanzania. Mary dedicated her life to social activism and supported the Lost Boys of Sudan. She established connection with Oakland and her biological family especially her mother and feels satisfied. Mary Williams works as a fundraiser for the IRC (International Rescue Committee) a non-governmental organization which assists refugees and people displaced by war, those who suffer due to natural disaster in more than 40 countries. Mary is an active member of this organization. In the success of Mary Williams as a writer, explorer, activist and social worker her family background both biological and adopted has contributed a lot.

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